

BOM Table

Part No.	Part Name	Quantity	Category	Cost/\$	Source
1	Arduino Uno	1	Micro controller	23.5	Amazon
2	Arduino UNO USB Data Sync Cable	1	Patch cable	7.9	Amazon
3	MegaMoto board	1	Motor Driver	44.99	Robot Power
4	Switch	1	Plastic	0.8	Amazon
5	Eppendorf Tube	12	Polypropylene	1.8	Eppendorf
6	Multicolored Dupont Wire	1	Connection	6.98	Amazon
7	AC-DC 24V Adapter Power Supply	1	Power Input	19.99	Amazon
8	Infrared Reflective Sensor	1	Sensor	1.99	Amazon
9	Silicone Wire 18AWG	1	Copper wire for connection	2.28	Amazon
10	Mini Fuse	1	Fast Blow Glass Fuses	0.59	Amazon
11	DC Motor	1	SciSpin mini motor	33.4	SCIQUIP
12	Rotor Cap	1	PLA	2	3D Printing Lab UCL
13	Centrifuge rotor	1	PLA	3	3D Printing Lab UCL
14	Small Metric Screws	20	M3-16mm	0.39	Amazon
15	Zinc Plated Hex Socket Head Screws	6	M4-25mm	0.59	Amazon
16	Adaptive Bottom Plate (130*90*6mm)	1	(Cast Al Plate)	12.9	UCL Workshop
17	Back acces panel	1	Main Structure Back	8.9	UCL Workshop
18	Bottom cover	1	Cover Plate for assembly	7.8	UCL Workshop
19	bottom plate	1	Bottom Plate for assembly	7.8	UCL Workshop
20	Side Plate	2	Side Plate for assembly	14.6	UCL Workshop
21	Top Cover	1	Top Cover for Guard	15.4	UCL Workshop
22	Top motor plate	1	Motor Plate for for assembly	12.9	UCL Workshop
Total Cost = 236.5\$					

Links for Consumptions

Arduino UNO: [Amazon.com: Arduino Uno REV3 \[A000066\]](https://www.amazon.com/Arduino-Uno-REV3-A000066/) : Electronics

Arduino Data Sync Cable: [Amazon.com: 3M Arduino UNO USB Data Sync Cable for Arduino Mega 2560 Rev 3 R3 Microcontroller](https://www.amazon.com/3M-Arduino-UNO-USB-Data-Sync-Cable-for-Arduino-Mega-2560-Rev-3-R3-Microcontroller/) : Electronics

MegaMoto For Arduino: [Robot Power Products - MegaMoto Motor Control Shield for Arduino](https://www.robotpowerproducts.com/megamoto-motor-control-shield-for-arduino/)

Mini Rocker Switch: [Amazon.com: DaierTek Mini Rocker Switch 12V 20A T85 2 Pin SPST Small ON Off Switch 120V 10A ON and Off Rocker Toggle KCD1 Switch Pre-Wired Black for Automotive, Car -10Pack](https://www.amazon.com/DaierTek-Mini-Rocker-Switch-12V-20A-T85-2-Pin-SPST-Small-ON-Off-Switch-120V-10A-ON-and-Off-Rocker-Toggle-KCD1-Switch-Pre-Wired-Black-for-Automotive-Car-10Pack/) : Sports & Outdoors

Multicolored Dupont Wire: [Amazon.com: ELEGOO 120pcs Multicolored Dupont Wire 40pin Male to Female, 40pin Male to Male, 40pin Female to Female Breadboard Jumper Ribbon Cables Kit Compatible with Arduino Projects](https://www.amazon.com/ELEGOO-120pcs-Multicolored-Dupont-Wire-40pin-Male-to-Female-40pin-Male-to-Male-40pin-Female-to-Female-Breadboard-Jumper-Ribbon-Cables-Kit-Compatible-with-Arduino-Projects/) : Electronics

AC-DC 24V Adapter Power Supply: [Amazon.com: Onerbl 24V AC/DC Adapter Compatible with Polk DYS602-240250W P/N DYS602-240250-12B02B DYS602-240250-15714A DC24V 2.5A 60W 24VDC 24.0V Switching Mode Power Supply Cord Cable Battery Charger Mains PSU](https://www.amazon.com/Onerbl-24V-AC-DC-Adapter-Compatible-with-Polk-DYS602-240250W-P-N-DYS602-240250-12B02B-DYS602-240250-15714A-DC24V-2.5A-60W-24VDC-24.0V-Switching-Mode-Power-Supply-Cord-Cable-Battery-Charger-Mains-PSU/) : Electronics

IR Sensor: [WWZMDiB 3Pcs 3.3-5V TCRT5000 Infrared Reflective Sensor IR Photoelectric](https://www.wenzel.com/3-pcs-3.3-5v-tcrt5000-infrared-reflective-sensor-ir-photoelectric/)

Switch Barrier Line Obstacle Avoidance Module Tracing Sensor Tracing Module for Arduino Smart Car Robot: Amazon.com: Industrial & Scientific

18 AWG Silicon wire: Super Soft 2 Pin Black Red Silicone Cable 28awg 26 24 22 20 18 16 14 12awg 10awg 8awg High Temperature Resistant Copper Wire (18 AWG, 5): Amazon.com: Tools & Home Improvement

Fast Blow Glass Fuses: BOJACK Mini Fuse 3.6x10 mm 2.5 A 2.5 amp 125 V 125 Volt 0.14x0.39 Inch F2.5AL125V Fast Blow Glass Fuses(Pack of 10 Pcs): Amazon.com: Tools & Home Improvement

DC Motor: SciSpin Mini Microfuge | Mini Centrifuges & Microcentrifuges (sciquip.co.uk)

Eppendorf 1.5 mL Tube: <https://www.eppendorf.com/gb-en/Products/Laboratory-Consumables/Tubes/Eppendorf-Safe-Lock-Tubes-p-0030120086>

Formlab SLA Resin: <https://formlabs.com/uk/store/materials/black-resin/>